

PROJECT HUSAY A READING STRATEGY DERIVED FROM GENRE BASED APPROACH TO ENHANCE SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS' READING COMPREHENSION

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ABSTRACT

Based on the reading assessment, majority of students' fall into almost and low proficient literacy categories. Indicates that students could read, however, their understanding of the text made it difficult for them to respond to questions. Thus, this study was designed in testing the effectiveness of Project HUSAY a Genre Based approach, reading intervention, in improving the reading comprehension skills of Grade 12 students who were struggling. The research goal was to identify the students' reading comprehension skills before and after the intervention implementation, to determine the significant difference in performance, and assess students' interest in teachers' strategies and reading activities. The subjects were 39 Grade 12 students. The methods used were classroom action research approach with a descriptive comparative research design and purposive sampling. Data was collected using reading comprehension tests, observations, interviews, and survey questionnaires. Before the intervention was employed, 17 students were categorized as frustration level, indicates lack of comprehension, while 19 students at instructional level, requiring additional support. Only 3 students were at the independent level of proficiency. After the implementation, students at the frustration level decreased to 3, while those at the instructional level increased by 21. The results of the study showed significant gain, the number of students at the independent level increase to 15, indicating an improvement in reading comprehension. Notably, a significant difference exists between the pre and post-test with the p-value (0.0080). The intervention posits a positive effect revealing to be a more effective strategy than traditional methods for enhancing students' reading comprehension skills.

Keywords: *Project HUSAY, Reading Comprehension, Grade 12 Students, Genre Based Approach, t-test*

INTRODUCTION

From the Reading Assessment recently conducted, the result shows that most of the students' literacy level belongs to the nearly proficient and low proficient and it was found out that the students could read but their level of reading comprehension impedes their ability to answer the questions. Thus, reading comprehension can be understood as a deep mental process in order to appreciate and recognize essential information within the text. As defined by Flavell (1985), comprehension in terms of the connection of the reader's prior knowledge and the text which generates meaning. He defines it as an internal process, and that it can only be activated through certain external developments that allow the readers to reach higher reading comprehension levels. It was also supported by Troyka and Thewett (2009) who say that reading comprehension is a complex, diverse process. As, reading encompasses more than decoding characters in a text; it implies the interpretation of what an author intends to say to an audience. According to Wallace (2001), reading is not feasible without understanding in this order of thoughts. He also added that comprehension is the form of the presentation of text followed by post-reading questions on the text.

In terms of understanding reading comprehension, many students had difficulty in understanding various text books. The researcher assumed that it was caused by several factors. First, due to the learning loss caused by the distance learning from the pandemic. The COVID-19 pandemic greatly affects students' performance all through the learning areas and most specially the reading comprehension of the learners, for they are not obliged to read when they are at home, for the students also disregard the responsibility to read the Learning Activity Sheets given to them by their teachers, for the reason that everything is accessible to the internet and they could find the answers to the activity given without exerting tremendous efforts. The second was students' lack of vocabulary mastery. If the students did not have enough vocabulary, of course it would be difficult for them to comprehend the reading text. The other factor was the students' lack of ability of recognizing the grammar because mastering grammar was also essential in understanding the text, such as; sentence pattern, syntax and others. The students must have the familiarity for those terms. Then, it was about students' passiveness toward reading. They highly regarded reading as fun and engaging if they find interest from the reading materials and find no inquisitiveness if they see the text as dreary. Lastly, it can be the medium of instruction yet to be employed by the teacher in teaching reading.

Evidently, these problems arise because the teacher did not apply the effective reading strategies yet in order to motivate the students become more active and creative in learning reading. As stated by Anderson (2008), to make students become active and get involved in reading activities, it is needed to teach them the various reading strategies' because reading with various strategies would create students to be critical and interested

learners. Thus, the researcher wants to apply the reading strategies derived from the theory of Genre Based approach and it is called as PROJECT HUSAY, which derived from the Filipino word which means EXCELLENCE as the project aims excellence for students Reading Level. In addition, Genre refers to a class of communicative events such as a seminar presentation, a university lecture, or an academic essay (Paltridge, 2001). In relation, Richards, et al (Paltridge, 2001) define genre as a particular class of events that are considered by a discourse community to be the same type. Example given there are prayer, sermons, conversations, songs, and speeches. Moreover, the key to the concept of genre is the “purpose” the piece of writing works. Initiated by Halliday’s work in the 1960s and 1970s, the Systemic Functional School of Linguistics pioneered this method. Furthermore, Gerot and Wignell (1995) compile kinds of genre in a different form namely, exposition (analytical), anecdote, report, exposition, narrative, discussion, news item, procedure, explanation, and description. They then separate those kinds into humanities and technological categories, technical documents pertaining to technical work or workshops, such as arguments, metalwork, reports, and so on.

The researcher aims high to promote the right of every learner for a quality, and equitable learning. As learning is best conceived as a process, not in terms of outcomes. As to improve learning in higher education, the primary focus should be on engaging students in a process that best enhances their learning- a process that includes feedback on the effectiveness of their learning effort Kolb and Kolb (2009). Similarly, the researcher believes that readers who have good reading comprehension can grasp the meaning and the organization of the writer’s idea. Wherein the readers bring their previous knowledge and experience into relation with their present reading; compare the facts and arguments presented by the authors. And it was supported by the idea of Harris (1969) where he explains that reading comprehension can be gained from several skills. They are; the students large amount of vocabulary, the students skill in identifying unfamiliar words, the students good eye-movement habits, the students proper habits of posture, holding books, etc., the students speed and fluency in silent reading, the students develop oral reading skill; phrasing, expression, and pitch. With that, the researcher believes that through this intervention and research-based activities it can develop an effective learning reading comprehension.

Research Questions

This study intends to determine the effect of the Project HUSAY to the Senior High School Students that are lagging behind in their Reading Comprehension skills of the school with the school ID 304898 of Marihatag District towards the improvement of performance, School Year 2022-2023.

Specifically, the study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of performance of the students that are lag behind in terms of:
 - 1.1. Reading Comprehension skills?
2. What is the level of performance of the students that are lag behind after Project HUSAY implementation in terms of:
 - 2.1. Reading Comprehension skills?

3. Is there a significant difference on the level of performance of the students that are lag behind as compared to after Project HUSAY implementation?
4. What is the level of performance of the students interest towards teachers teaching strategies?
5. What is the level of students reading activities?

Hypothesis

Ho: There is no significant difference on the level of performance of the students that are lag behind as compared to after Project HUSAY implementation?

METHODOLOGY

The participants of this research were the Grade-12 senior high school students of a school with school ID 304898 of Marihatag District. The class comprised 39 students thus, the researcher used purposive sampling technique. This research was classroom action research. The action research in the language classroom is a tool for teachers and curriculum development to improve the way of teaching. It aims at increasing teachers' understanding of classroom teaching and learning process (Kemmis and Mc Taggart: 1982). Accordingly, the goal of this action research is to improve the quality of the teaching and learning experience. In this case, the researcher intended to increase the reading comprehension of Marihatag District Grade 12 Senior High School students.

The descriptive comparative design will be used in this investigation. Descriptive design is used to collect data on variables without altering the surroundings. Descriptive designs, according to Gray et al. (2013), can be used to discover difficulties, make decisions in actual practice, or even construct theories. Since the research contrasted characteristics from past activities' performances and the current results without changing the independent variable, the researchers adopted the comparative design within descriptive research.

In gathering the data, the researcher will use three kinds of instruments. They were reading comprehension test, observation, interview and questionnaire. The questionnaire that will be used in the study will be the instrument used in the recently conducted group screening test from the Division office, the researcher will administer the instrument individually to specifically measure the level of reading comprehension of the learners. As this will also be used to guide the interview and to know whether the students had actively involved (solving students' passiveness) in the class activities. To know whether the students were passive or active in learning, it needed to know the characteristics of motivated students since motivation was one of the major factors for the students to be activated in learning activities. The interview will be based on the suggestions of Anderson et.al., (Yumaslinda, 2006) on the characteristics of students who had interest in learning.

To round things off, McManus (2001) identified the characteristics of active and passive students, which will serve as the foundation for our observations to complete the three instruments.

This action research process was adapted from the concept in the study of (Fitrawati, 2004) this study is conducted in three cycles. Each cycle consisted of four to five meetings. Every meeting was similar to two hours (2x40 minutes). So, there will be twelve-thirteen meetings during research process.

The Cycles are dealing with these three steps:

1. Plan

In plan step, the researcher had known the problems of teaching reading. They were students' passiveness and teacher's teaching strategies. Based on these problems, the plan activities were:

- a) Designing class room reading activities which might be done to complement the reading strategies derived from genre-based approach
- b) Making a copy of the text to the students
- c) Distributing the copy of anecdote text entitled Blessing behind Tragedy to the students

2. Action

The action activities in cycle 1 were:

- a) Introduction. The teacher warmed up the class by greeting and attracting students' interest
- b) The teacher will distribute the copies of reading text to each student
- c) The teacher will implement the reading strategies derived from genre based approach in three reading phases: pre-reading, whilst reading and post reading
- d) The teacher will divide the students into groups of six. Each group was led by one student as a group leader
- e) The teacher will monitor the group discussion by walking around the class

3. Observation

- a) The teacher will observe the class while she was implementing the reading strategies
- b) The teacher will do the checklist to know how many students were active, what the students' activities were, and how the students worked in the group
- c) The teacher will observe the students during the process of learning reading
- d) The teacher will observe the students during the discussion and presentation

4. Reflection

At the end of cycle 1, the researcher will distribute the questioners. The questioners ascertain at knowing how the reading strategies derived from genre-based approach could improve students' reading comprehension. In other words, the questioners were used as guidance to identify the improvement of students' reading comprehension.

Later, the data collected will be analyzed from the observation checklist, questioners, and interview to make conclusion about any development from the students learning behavior. Finally, the researcher will plan pattern of improving students' reading comprehension

found in cycle 1 and made plan for cycle 2 to continue the progress achieved in cycle 1. In cycle 2 and 3, the activities were similar to those in cycle 1, but there were some different emphases due to the revised plan.

The performance level of the respondents who fall short behind in reading comprehension skills is identified through computing the use of frequency, percentage distributions, mean and rank. On the other hand, to compute the significant difference on the level of performance of the pupils that are lag behind as compared to after Project HUSAY implementation as base on the result from the test utilize during pre-test and posttest thru the adapted questionnaire from the recently conducted reading assessment, the statistical test that the study utilize is a t-test since the data are obtained within two given tests. According to (Snedecor and Cochran, 1989), a t-test is a statistical test that is used to compare the means of two groups. Additionally, it is often used in hypothesis testing to determine whether a process or treatment actually has an effect on the population of interest, or whether two groups are different from one another. Furthermore, it is commonly used to test if a new process or treatment is superior to a current process or treatment which is suitable in this study. The study started on October 2022 and ended on January 2023, covering the second quarters.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The level of performance of the students that are lag behind in terms of Reading Comprehension Skills

Table 1: *The level of performance of the students that are lag behind in terms of Reading Comprehension Skills*

	Enrollment			14 & above			8 to 13			1 to 7			0		
				Independent			Instructional			Frustration			Non-Reader		
	M	F	T	M	F	T	M	F	T	M	F	T	M	F	T
Students' Scores	2	1	3	0	3	3	11	8	19	13	4	17	0	0	0

The table presented the scores of the students that are lag behind in their reading comprehension skills in which Project HUSAY is not yet being applied. It is revealed from the table that there is a record of 17 number of students under frustration which indicates that these learners can read but lack of comprehension. In addition, 19 students also belong to Instructional level, an indicator that learners can comprehend but with provision. Moreover, only 3 out of 39 Grade 12 students belong to Independent level of proficiency.

Anchored to the study of Mollaneda (2015) reported by Ambray (2017) delivery of learning experiences or situations secured understanding. As such, a rich environment and instructional strategies is needed. These resources and tools assessed the learner's attention, simulated thinking, and promoted understanding to make learning more engaging. According to Booker, one benefit of integrating or participating in trial-and-error environment with peers was that kids could talk about problems as they arose and quickly obtain feedback. Additionally, he pointed out that students could build on their prior learning and created links between the problem-solving process and their everyday lives. Thus, the passive attitude also of the students were being observed as one factor that yields to the low result of the score as the students lack of vocabulary that they could not comprehend the reading text and express their ideas.

During the Implementation of the Intervention

The level of performance of the students that are lag behind during Project HUSAY implementation in terms of Reading Comprehension Skills

Table 2: *The level of performance of the students that are lag behind after Project HUSAY implementation in terms of Reading Comprehension Skills*

	Enrollment			14 & above			8 to 13			1 to 7			0		
				Independent			Instructional			Frustration			Non-Reader		
	M	F	T	M	F	T	M	F	T	M	F	T	M	F	T
Students' Scores	2	1	3	3	4	7	15	5	20	6	6	12	0	0	0

Table 2 shows the result of the students during the implementation of Project HUSAY and it reveals a slight increase of scores of the learners, these could might have been the students did not really understand yet the concept of reading strategies derived from genre-based approach so they could not implement them in reading. They lack self-confidence to answer and ask questions from the teacher and other students. They were afraid of making mistake. So, they felt in doubt in any reading activities. However, this result also prevails an improvement on the level of reading comprehension of the students as the number of the students in the independent level had doubled.

According to (Duffy in Richard & Renandya, 2002) who were quoted in Fitrawati (2012) study, the reader should have effective reading strategies to gain the better reading comprehension. Reading strategies can be as plans for solving problems encountered in constructing meaning. Defined as strategy is a tool to achieve the reading goal. In comparison, the goal of teaching reading strategies is to create students become strategic readers. Being strategic reader is not easy, it takes time and needs a lot of practices.

Post Data Observation

The level of performance of the students that are lag behind after Project HUSAY implementation in terms of Reading Comprehension Skills

Table 3: The level of performance of the students that are lag behind after Project HUSAY implementation in terms of Reading Comprehension Skills

	Enrollment			14 & above			8 to 13			1 to 7			0		
				Independent			Instructional			Frustration			Non-Reader		
	M	F	T	M	F	T	M	F	T	M	F	T	M	F	T
Students' Scores	2 4	1 5	3 9	7	8	15	14	7	21	3	0	3	0	0	0

The table displayed the scores of the students that are lag behind after project HUSAY implementation it shows that the level of students under frustration were smaller as per record there are 3 learners compare to the results from the pre-implementation of project HUSAY. Added to that, the number of students under instructional level increases with 21 number of learners and most significantly the number of learners under independent level of proficiency had increased into 15 which means that the reading comprehension level of the students had improved after the implementation of the intervention.

After the implementation of Project HUSAY to the grade 12 students, the posttest result showed their score. It can be seen that the pretest scores had increased significantly. It was evident from a comparison of the scores form pretest and posttest results that with the project HUSAY being applied to the learners the group had learned more than before the implementation.

Supported by the study of Acero (2010), the researcher overemphasized that learning is good when it provides learning experience or situations that will ensure understanding. Rich environments, educational resources and equipment are necessary for effective instruction. To make learning more meaningful, materials and tools challenge learners' attention, initiate thinking and help with understanding.

Students' interest toward teaching strategies in the implementation of the Intervention

Table 4: The result of students' interest toward teaching strategies

No.	Items	Always (%)	Often (%)	Seldom (%)	Never (%)
1	Students' interest in teacher strategies	29(74%)	8(21%)	2(5%)	-
2	The strategies help the students in reading the text	32(82%)	6(15%)	1(3%)	-
3	Students persistence in using the strategies	30(77%)	8(21%)	2(5%)	-

4	The students' motivation in reading activity	28(72%)	8(21%)	3(8%)	-
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The table illustrates that during the implementation of project HUSAY the researcher had observed the following traits showed by the students toward teaching strategies and it shows that in the process students implicated positive attitude and interest in the conduct of the study. These suggest that with the student's positive engagement of the study gives a positive result in the reading comprehension of the learners.

The result of students' reading activities in the implementation of project HUSAY

Table 5: *The result of students' reading activities*

No.	Items	Always (%)	Often (%)	Seldom (%)	Never (%)
1	Interaction with teacher and friends	22(56%)	12(31%)	5(13%)	-
2	Being persistent in facing reading difficulties	24(62%)	10(26%)	5(13%)	-
3	Wanting to get feedback	18(46%)	12(31%)	6(15%)	3(8%)
4	Having self confidence in reading	20(51%)	10(26%)	7(18%)	2(5%)
5	Competing positively	15(38%)	20(51%)	3(8%)	1(3%)
6	Having high discipline in using time	17(44%)	18(46%)	3(8%)	1(3%)
7	Not easy to be satisfied with the reading result	14(36%)	19(49%)	5(13%)	1(3%)
8	Having willingness to work in group	30(77%)	6(15%)	3(8%)	-

It can be seen in the table the results of students' reading activities during the conduct of the implementation of project HUSAY.

It implies that with student's active involvement in the reading process students learn in their best. As it revealed in the table that most of the students had actively participated and cooperated in the study.

The significant difference on the level of performance of the students that are lag behind as compared to after Project HUSAY implementation

Table 6: *The Significant difference on the level of performance of the students that are lag behind as compared to after Project HUSAY implementation*

Scores	Mean	Computed Value	p-value	Decision	Conclusion
Before project HUSAY implementation	8.4	0.4965	0.0080	Reject H ₀	Sig.

After project HUSAY implementation	10.25				
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The p-value (0.0080) was smaller than 0.4965-3.2035 so based on the aforementioned data, this difference is considered to be statistically significant. It is noteworthy that the scores between the pre and post implementation of project HUSAY indicates a big difference. With that, project HUSAY as a reading intervention suggest to be more successful approach in enhancing the reading comprehension of the learners than with the conventional approach.

As mentioned by Mercado (2019) students are more interested in experimental approach than conventional classroom exercises. As students tend to be more excited and engaging. In addition, with support from the study of (Arévalo, 2019) the overall findings show that students' reading comprehension, writing, motivation and autonomy improved after the implementation of Genre Based Approach; as a result, the students were able to understand, explain and recreate the genres that were part of the study.

Conclusions

A key component of academic achievement is the capacity to understand what one reads; however, many students struggle greatly in this area. Identifying the need to assist students' who struggle with reading comprehension, this study launched Project HUSAY, a focused intervention meant to improve these vital abilities. The study's findings offer strong proof of the project's success in raising the participating students' reading comprehension and general academic engagement.

The students' reading comprehension performance was concerning prior to the implementation of Project HUSAY. Most of the students were lag behind in understanding the texts they were reading and were either at the instructional or frustrated levels. It was evident that many of these learners' struggle in their academic undertakings in the absence of support, since there were only 3 students at the independent level and 17 in the frustration group. The poor competence levels made the researcher how urgently the need to adopt a more successful and interesting teaching strategy.

The study had showed that the students' skills in comprehending the material they read were much enhanced with the introduction of Project HUSAY. Post-intervention statistics showed that the number of pupils at the independent level more than doubled, from 3 to 15. It is clear from this significant progress that students were able to progress from struggling to competent readers with the help of Project HUSAY. In addition to gains in reading level, there was a significant decrease in the percentage of students' experiencing frustration. These adjustments show that the intervention have positive effect in addressing the students' comprehension issues when reading and allowing them to interact more thoroughly and independently with the given texts.

Additionally, the study found using t-test that students' performance before and after the intervention shows that the improvement in reading comprehension was statistically significant and that mean scores increased from 8.4 to 10.25 (p-value = 0.0080). This result emphasizes how Project HUSAY generated positive significant difference in improving reading comprehension abilities, especially for students who were lag behind.

The researcher had also showed another key factor contributing to the success of a teaching strategy, it was the students' positive response to the intervention being applied. It does reveal that students showed a great deal of interest in the techniques, responding they were interesting and practical. Given their increased motivation to engage in active learning, students increased interest contributed to better performance. As a means of sustaining student interest and promoting improved learning outcomes, the study emphasizes creative and interactive teaching strategies is substantial.

In the level of students' reading activities, many demonstrated persistence in overcoming reading difficulties and showed a willingness to collaborate with their peers. This active involvement in the reading process is crucial for developing strong comprehension skills and reflects the effectiveness of the intervention in creating a supportive and engaging learning environment.

Thus, it is imperative to create a more engaging and encouraging learning environment to address the specific needs of struggling readers and achieve proficiency in reading comprehension.

Recommendations

Based on the summary of findings and conclusions the researcher recommends that teachers should establish a more interesting and engaging teaching methods to maintain students' interest and foster active participation by incorporating reading strategies, as such, the Project HUSAY. Also, conduct future researches that expand research on Project HUSAY to evaluate its long-term impact and effectiveness across a larger student population. Teachers should also, regularly monitor and assess students' reading comprehension to identify those needing additional support and make timely adjustments to teaching strategies. Finally, workshops and seminars should be organized for the training and retraining of teachers on incorporating reading strategies specifically the Project HUSAY: Genre Based Approach reading strategy to improve students' reading comprehension.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In this research study, substantial effort was carried out in accordance with ethical rules. First, the researcher made certain that no harm was imposed on the students. Second, informed consent was obtained, and data confidentiality was maintained with great caution. The participants provided their agreement to participate in the study in accordance with the Data Privacy Act. The data's privacy and confidentiality were protected. Unintentional publication of personal information about its citizens is prohibited

by the Philippine Data Privacy Act (DPA) of 2012 (Fabito et al., 2018). Nor were the objectives of the study misrepresented. In addition, it is clear that there is an avoidance of false information, honesty, openness, and the use of offensive, discriminatory, and unpleasant terminology.

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